

Information technology of surveys and diagnostics of underground pipelines

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Інформаційна технологія обстежень і діагностики підземних трубопроводів

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Contents of the report

- Need for periodic inspections of underground pipelines (UP)
- Analysis of the state of the problem
- The drawbacks of the contact method of the UP observations
- Advantages of contactless survey methods
- Mathematical model of the EM field of an UP as Theoretical Foundations
- Development of contactless methods measurement of currents
- Development of potentials measurements
- Improvement of pipelines survey. Measurement processing
- Results of practical use

Fig. 1. Underground pipeline (UP),
insulation coating and cathod protection

The main disadvantages of contact methods

- The complexity of providing reliable contacts with the UP and the soil, at transitions under rivers, in wetlands and in vegetation thickets on the route;
- Unreliability of contacts of the electrodes with the soil with high resistance to the surface of the earth (dry soils, asphalt, etc.);
- Limited range of activities (local character of control).

Theoretical bases of the method of contactless measurements of underground pipelines electric currents and non-destructive corrosion protection testing

Triune mathematical model

of an electromagnetic field of an underground pipeline.

Methods of **contactless** measurement of UP currents

Radial (gradient) 1-4, 16; azimuthal (parallax) 6-9, 17; invariant 10-12,15

INTEGRAL observation

Current distribution in 3 pipelines.

DIFFERENTIAL observation

Non-contact measurement of current by BIT-KVP.

- Distribution of cathode protection current J , pipe depth h ,
- current consumption ΔJ ,
- relative leakage of current $\Delta J/J\Delta z$
- and transient resistance $R_{mg}(n)$.

$$R_{mg}(n) = R_b \pi D / \delta J_n$$

Differential inspection of the main gas pipeline

Determination of places of **unsatisfactory insulation** of UP; **critical** current attenuation

← Criterion of unsatisfactory insulation

Distribution of CPS current and relative expense dJ / Jdl in the section of the main pipeline by measurements of BIT-KVP.

$$\delta J_{cr} = 0,2\sqrt{f \sigma_g}$$

Pipe-to-Ground Transition Resistance (distribution !)

- MoData

- BIT-KVP

Inspection of the main gas pipeline (10 km):
 MoData equipment (potentials U , dU) and
 BIT-KPP (distribution of current, flow of current into the pipeline,
transient resistance R_{pg} , depth of UP)

Determination of cathode **protection current** density and the difference in **potentials** on UP insulation

Cathodic protection current ΔI_n in the area of UP (constant current component)

$$\Delta I_n = |J_n - J_{n-1}| / K_n$$

harmonic coefficient $K_n = V_x / E_x$

The **current density** of the cathode protection for the UP area $I_n = z_n - z_{n-1}$

$$i_n = \Delta I_n / s_n = \Delta I_n / \pi D l_n, \quad (\text{A/m}^2)$$

The difference in potentials on UP insulation $\Delta E_{in} = E_g + E_{pol} - E_n,$

E_n – measurement of the potential of the pipe-EP on the site n ;

E_g – drop of potential in the soil over UP

$$E_g = E_x \frac{\ln\left(\frac{4h}{D} - 1\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{x^2}{h^2} + 1\right)}$$

$E_x = E_g$ if the distance between points M and N is $x = h \sqrt{2\left(\frac{2h}{D} - 1\right)}$

E_{pol} – polarization potential of UP

$$U_p = U_{mg} - V_{mg} \cdot U_{gg} / V_{gg}$$

Polarization resistance $R_{pol} = R_{mg} - R_i.$

LOCAL observation.

Points D and E for CMC J_n and electrodes M and N for measuring voltages $V_x = V_{gg}, U_x$ when examining an underground pipeline.

Specific soil resistance ρ_g on the UP route, near pipe

$$\rho_g = \frac{2\pi l_n V_{gg}}{\Delta J_n \ln(1 + x^2 / h^2)}$$

MPP with GPS

MPP connection scheme

**Measured values
and underground pipelines corrosion protection
parameters determination**

Apparatus		Виміри	Параметри ПКЗ підземного трубопроводу									
БИТ-КВП	ОПТ+B2		ΔJ_n	$\delta J \approx \alpha$	$R_{\Pi}(z)$	ρ_g	R_{Mg}	R_i	k_j	i_n	R_p	U_p
+		J_n	+	+	+	+	+	+		+	+	
+		h				+		+			+	
		Δz		+	+	+	+	+			+	
+	+	V_x				+		+	+	+	+	+
	+	U_x							+	+	+	+
	+	U_{Mg}									+	+
+	+	V_{Mg}					+	+			+	+

□

Contactless current meter BVC-2 + GPS

Distribution of the corrosion protection current,
depth of occurrence,
transition resistance pipe-earth,
Control of the insulation state.
Place on electronic maps.

Contactless measurements of the CPI current in the area of UP by the BVC apparatus

Distribution amperage J along the pipeline section
from the measurements of equipment BVC
and calculation of the relative consumption of current.

Contactless surveys of underground pipelines in conditions of interference

Fig. 2. Distribution of the amperage J along the pipeline:

- 1 - Results of measurements;
- 2 - Approximation polynomial measurements 9th degree;
- 3 - Approximation of linear dependencies.

Processing of an array of current measurements:
calculation of the distribution of **the transient resistance**
of the UP in the area of the conditions of the **interference**

Fig. 4. Calculation of the transfer resistance:

- 1 - by averaging across the site survey;
- 2 - approximation by a broken line with direct approximation;
- 3 - the approximation polynomial of 9th degree is given.

Distribution along the main pipeline relative current consumption ($\delta J_{cr} = 0.36\% / m$)

Distribution along the main pipeline of the U_p voltage according to the PPM data.

Distribution **transient impedance** "pipe-earth" R_{mg} and of **insulation** R_i .

Conclusions

- **1. New information technology** of diagnostic examinations of underground pipelines on the **basis of contactless measurement of currents** is developed.
- 2. For the first time, it was possible to expedite the detection of abnormally high **expenses of current** in the area of the cathodic protection installation (CPI) of the UP. In these places there is the worst state of UP insulation, so they need to first of all control the state of electrochemical **corrosion protection** (to measure the polarization potential).
- Then contact measurements of potentials along the entire length of the CPI zone may not be performed. These significantly reduces the number of field measurements for the testing and diagnostics of the UP anti-corrosion protection.
- **3. Integration** of this technology (with the created means of technical and methodological support) into the overall system of anti-corrosion protection **increases** the efficiency and **informativeness of the surveys**. It gives the opportunity to switch from regular maintenance to maintenance or repair on a technical condition **to prevent damage**.
- It increase reliability and extend the useful life of expensive and important underground pipelines and related structures.

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Дякую за увагу

Thank you for attention